

OA Book Usage Data Trust | Board Committee Member Role Description

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The OA Book Usage Data Trust's Mission and Vision

As described in the OAeBU DT effort's impact-driven service model (<https://zenodo.org/record/5579257>), the inaugural mission of the OAeBU DT effort is to "Champion strategies for improved publication and management of open-access books by exchanging reliable usage data in a trusted, equitable, and community-governed way." It does this to advance the OA book publishing and discovery ecosystem towards a future where there is the "community-governed sharing of quality, interoperable OA book usage data."

Overall Board of Trustees Purpose and Function

OA Book Usage Data Trustee duties are set forth in the OAeBU DT's guiding governance documentation (<https://zenodo.org/record/5703745>):

The OAeBU Board of Trustees is a working board composed of elected Trustees led by an Executive Committee of Board Officers. Trustees share responsibility for:

- strategy development and direction setting
- supervising the OAeBU DT Executive Director (ED), in conjunction with the Fiscal Sponsor
- monitoring effort-wide financials, including project budget-to-actuals and
- agreements related to the OAeBU DT effort
- supervising hosting and administration arrangements for Fiscal Sponsors

While the full Board meets six times per year, Standing and Ad-hoc Committees chaired by Trustees advance Board objectives and meet more or less frequently. Both Trustees and community members may participate in Board Committees at the discretion of the Board.

Committee Member Role Description

This role requires active participation and engagement. Though each Board Committee has its own charge, each Committee Member is responsible for:

- recommending action to the Board for structural changes to the OAeBU DT effort to ensure the compliance with its purpose, legal and fiduciary duties
- promoting and adhering to the Board's governance guidelines and policies
- supporting the efforts of the Board and carrying out individual assignments made by the chair
- engaging and collaborating professionally with commercial, academic, and non-profit audiences to promote the mission of OAeBU
- complying with OAeBU governance guidelines

Committee Members are accountable to the OAeBU Data Trust Board Chair and/or Board Committee Chair.

Primary Responsibilities

Participation

- attend and participate in scheduled meetings
- be willing to accept special assignments and duties as needed
- embrace on-going conversations to increase the engagement and continuity of the Board Committee's work; platforms include Slack and Trello

External Engagement and Advocacy

- publicly represent and promote the mission of OAeBU
- participate in community events that elevate the profile of OAeBU
- assist in the recruitment of participants

Qualifications

Qualifications included in the [Governance Documentation](#) extend to Committee Members, including:

- creative thinker; embracing new ideas; passionate about developing the potential of OAeBU
- inclusive in decision-making and problem-solving; embracing ideas from all perspectives
- willing and available to put time and energy towards the work
- openness to the goals of both commercial and noncommercial actors in book publishing

Experience

Experience or interest in publishing, libraries, research infrastructure, scholarly communications or open scholarship.